

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM FOR DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE COMPETENCE OF
FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING

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Abstract. The article examines the issues of preparing students for pedagogical activity based on the use of innovative technologies, which is due to the insufficient orientation of the content of special and general educational subjects to solving this problem. Didactic conditions for introducing innovative pedagogical tasks and situations into the content of subjects at a pedagogical university are identified. Three types of innovative pedagogical tasks are identified.

Keywords: innovative technologies, innovative pedagogical tasks, pedagogical activity, public education, professional thinking.

INTRODUCTION

A modern teacher must be able to focus the educational process on the personality of the student, carry out pedagogical reflection, i.e. perceive and regulate his educational work as a process that focuses on the natural stages of personality formation, situations that reveal its creative potential, and not as a set of classes and events. The future teacher must master the technology of creating innovative situations with various educational functions. He must also be able to use an integrated system of educational and didactic tools when teaching students his subject, which will ensure the formation of personality in the future. At the same time, it is important for the future teacher to learn to teach his subject in close connection with different types of activities, social experience of students, and to apply methods of imitation modeling of various social situations. One of the main places in the system of preparing a student for upcoming pedagogical activity today is his ability to navigate in innovative processes occurring in the theory and practice of public education. As a means of developing the innovative thinking of the future teacher, we tested a system of pedagogical tasks (didactic conditions for introducing innovative pedagogical tasks and situations into the content of subjects of the pedagogical university were identified) [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order for a future teacher to perform pedagogical activity qualitatively, he should master his subject not only as a “pure” science, but also as a means of educating and developing students. The concept of “readiness for pedagogical activity” includes the mastery of specialized and general educational knowledge by the future teacher to the extent of their professional application. An important reserve for intensifying the process of forming a future specialist is the inclusion of tasks, problems, situations reflecting innovative processes in the content of teaching all university subjects. We are talking about fragments associated with the expansion of a certain problematic pedagogical situation, with the choice or assessment of ways to solve innovative problems that arise in pedagogical practice. Their purpose is to stimulate professional motivation and professional thinking of the future teacher. When tasks that require various innovations are included in the learning process, students become aware of the place and specificity of innovations in the structure of pedagogical activity and in the system of their future professional functions. A task helps organize a student’s activity, leads him to a clear understanding of the situation caused by a deficit of some vital resource,

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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setting goals for its transformation, and identifying conditions and methods of action. Any solution certainly includes intention, plan, creativity, giving meaning, taking on a certain responsibility, and evaluating the result. And these are already personal aspects of the solution. In this sense, a task is an event that requires a transition from one life situation to another [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It should be noted that the majority of studies are related to the use of innovative pedagogical tasks in practical classes in the disciplines of the psychological and pedagogical cycle. Innovative pedagogical tasks should be systematically and with appropriate dosage included in the study of university disciplines by students, which is a necessary condition for improving the professional focus of most special and general educational disciplines. The greatest innovative potential is possessed by tasks that require finding qualitatively new technologies of teaching and education (simulation and mathematical modeling, reference signals, integration of scientific information, educational and business games, etc.), teaching students the skills of analysis, explanation and evaluation of pedagogical phenomena, self-analysis and correction of their behavior. In this context, a certain number of didactic problems arise: what are the goals of introducing such tasks into the process of mastering “non-pedagogical” subjects, will this violate the specific logic of these disciplines, what can become the content of such innovations (especially in terms of reflecting innovative processes) and how should the process of their solution be organized, what is the influence of the use of pedagogical tasks-situations on the general professional development of students. In studying these problems, we relied on the analysis of the nature of pedagogical activity, the basis of which is the solution of a system of a certain kind of tasks related to the organization of the educational process, organically including elements of innovation. Innovative pedagogical tasks-situations considered in our study are connected with the main components of pedagogical activity, namely: analysis of the pedagogical situation, setting the goal of its transformation and selection of the necessary educational and didactic means for this, implementation of the project of pedagogical action in practice (within the framework of the conducted study this was carried out during the simulation game). We identified three types of innovative pedagogical tasks [4]:

- 1) orienting-analytical;
- 2) design-goal-setting;
- 3) practical-simulation.

CONCLUSION

Using innovative pedagogical tasks as one of the elements of teaching technology and analyzing the attitude of future teachers to fragments of professionally significant material, we noted that their interest in such classes increases if these classes include pedagogical tasks and professional information. Under the influence of these tasks, students realize both the general cultural and the professional significance of the general educational and specialized subject.

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